

THE OCCURRENCE OF STROKE DISEASE IN HUMANS AND IT'S
PHYSIOLOGICAL PROCESSES.

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Annotation: We know that by the present time, innovative technologies are developing and yet various new diseases are also developing. Various small factors are causing severe diseases. In this cited article, however, the occurrence of stroke disease in humans and the physiological processes observed in patients with this disease and changes in their psyche are cited.

Keywords: stroke, types, hemorrhagic stroke, ischemic stroke, cause, atherosclerosis, symptoms, treatment.

One of the most common diseases of the brain is stroke, which is a sudden neurological disease. In this disease, blood circulation in the cranial brain is caused by a strong disorder. In a stroke, blood flow to the brain occurs with a rupture of blood vessels in the brain. Two types of this disease occur mainly:

1. Hemorrhagic stroke is a disease that goes to the brain with a blood transfusion. Although this type of stroke appears suddenly in humans, however, the target of the disease is noticeable in advance. For examples, hypertension, and atherosclerosis, the brain suddenly gets a blood clot, often when a person is embarrassed. The signs that occur in this are nodding, headaches, dizziness, and an isthmus rises. In the case, the patient faints and vomiting redness is observed on the face, often deep often inhales wheezing.

2. Ischemic stroke is a disorder in which blood from the brain reaches brain tissue as a result of vascular thrombosis. In this case, softening of the brain tissue causes a cerebral

infarction. The signs in this are also vital such as headaches and dizziness that bring the symptoms to the surface. But the patient will be awake, the hands or feet will be numb and there will be paresis or paralysis. The ability to perceive disappears or decreases speech impaired. The patient is pale in color with the eyelids narrow, the pulse weak is felt very slowly. Body temperature will be normal. You can understand these cases very easily in pictures.

FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTE TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF STROKE DISEASE.

The effect of smoking and alcohol on the development of the disease. These harmful habits double the development of stroke compared to healthy people. Smoking and alcohol increase blood coagulation, accelerate the formation of thrombi (hardened blood clots) and damage the inner wall of the vessels. The vessel narrows. After that, blood supply to the brain tissue is disrupted. Quitting smoking sharply reduces the risk of developing a stroke and heart attack after 2-4 years. This is a phenomenon that has been proven.

ATHEROSCLEROSIS DISEASE ALSO DEVELOPS STROKE DISEASE.

That being said, with increasing age, atherosclerosis begins to occur a lot. Therefore, as age increases, the number of stroke cases increases. Cholesterol levels in the blood increase, the vessel walls become brittle, scars appear on the vessels, and the cholesterol substance gets stuck in the vessels, causing a stroke. low mobility increases the accumulation of cholesterol in the vessels which also leads to atherosclerosis, develops stroke and cardiovascular diseases. In people in constant motion, the heart promotes blood circulation by developing blood vessels well and reduces stroke.

The effect of stress on the disease. Scientists call the 20th century the age of stress. Because nowadays there are more and more diseases that arise due to nervous tension, namely stroke and heart attack. It is known that the stroke that we ask for people who have missed the disease turns out to be a severe depression before the development of this disease. Therefore, stress increases the development of the disease. Also, in a person with constant compression, the development of hypertonia disease, diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart diseases are observed a lot. All these are considered diseases that increase the state of being

a stroke. It is worth saying that physical labor and sports on a constant level are less exposed to mental - emotional tension. It is considered extremely important to prevent stroke.

OBSERVED CASES IN STROKE PATIENTS.

Since stroke is a cranial disease, the patient experiences a lot of neurological changes. As an example, this disease is observed on the right side of the brain such people experience paralysis and sensory disturbances on the left sides of the body. Damage to the right hemisphere will make the body structures unable to control the lateral left side of the other, which will remain the same. In some cases, cases of self-suffocation are observed, with a semi-paralyzed arm not attached to itself. Some patients will have a different left-hand hoodie that looks like his cat or beautiful toys, while patient cases of pampering him have been observed. But such cases are not recognized by the patient.

CHANGES IN THE PATIENT'S FACIAL STRUCTURE IN LEFT BRAIN STROKE.

The condition of patients when stroke is observed in the left hemisphere of the brain. The state of speech disorders and semi-paralysis of such patients is observed. Usually, the behavior of a person with speech disorders is also rapidly changeable. A sudden speech disorder changes the psychology of the patient so that he does not make sense by accepting the speech of those around him only without a touch. He cannot give his opinion. It becomes difficult to communicate with such patients, they do not fulfill what the doctor and loved ones say, fight quickly or cry, refuse to eat, pee at the bottom and make it too easy to take care of. For this, it will be very difficult for the doctor to work with such patients.

WHAT CHANGES OCCUR IN THE EMOTION OF PATIENTS.

The patient becomes self-numb, sometimes laughing at something not worth it. Naturally, they will be very capricious because the disorders of movement or speech separate it from nature. Their body is manifested in combination with a violation of the perception of the environment without pretending to be. For example, once patient leaves home a familiar person first cannot remember anything else. They become afraid of everything that means that whoever says something to the young child becomes gullible or ahsi. In stroke diseases, this condition is mild.

In order to avoid such unpleasant situations, everyone must first of all be attentive to the health of himself.

Nowadays, irritability situations are observed in any person these irritations develop not only stroke, but also the origin of other diseases.

In developed countries, such diseases are very rare because everyone pays great attention to their health. Because in developed countries, since each person gives a very high value to his health. In our country, we need to keep our elderly parents from getting nervous and suffering from depressions. Elderly people should be provided with peace of mind.

In order not to suffer from this disease, everyone needs to avenge himself. Young people should also be able to show affection to older people, keeping them away from all hard physical activities, keeping them away from the treats that offend them and taking them to different places to a new beautiful nature. In other words we must always keep the psyche homogeneous to keep them away from family treats. But it is never possible to limit yourself from the activities that will happen in society and in the family. A person who is completely separated from the family is also stressed, thinking that he is an unnecessary person.

USEFUL TIPS FOR STROKE PATIENTS AND THEIR RELATIVES.

First, a healthy psychological environment should be created around the womb, the patient. In recovery, the patient's mood comes first, while the patient, who is in a positive optimistic spirit, has recovered much faster than pessimistic patients. Therefore, if the doctor and the patient's ventricles must, in agreement, raise the patient's mood as much as possible, the patient's woman and children must always be able to convince the patient himself of his recovery by being a pole next to him so that the patient begins to convince himself to recover knowing that he has a place in society. Our brain is structured in such a way that when we command the brain to heal, our brain takes all the opportunity in our organ.

Semi-paralysis of the patient who has undergone a stroke and the absence of speech ability.

Since speech is the greatest blessing given to mankind, it is necessary to appeal to the authorities of this work on the restoration of this ability. With this work, a neuropsychologist or clinical speech therapist is engaged in this area. When the patient people in the strophe and begins to speak himself, his mood is increased, blood pressure is normalized, and half-paralysis in the limbs also recedes. We see that barge diseases or everything that a person does not like is turning out to be a complication of excessive compressibility or mental depressions and therefore create a healthy lifestyle, both in the family and in society. It is necessary to be able to follow the same created healthy lifestyle. Therefore, it is possible that every person will be able to restore his health. doctors can only warn. Everyone should pay serious attention to their own health itself!

Conclusion: Our conclusion is that stroke it is a serious condition that requires urgent medical attention and is important for treatment. Treatment can often include dissolving blood clots, controlling blood pressure, and providing adequate oxygen to the brain, depending on the patient's condition. The rehabilitation process is also important to help restore the patient's functions.

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